

Area-Selective Silicidation: Patterning Metal Silicides from the Bottom Up

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Driven by deeper insights into their nanoscale properties, the role of metal silicides in nanotechnology has recently been redefined. A central challenge in this field is the development of new methods for the controlled synthesis of low-dimensional silicides, whose promising properties are often theoretically predicted but remain difficult to validate experimentally. To address this challenge, area-selective (AS) silicidation is introduced as a bottom-up approach that enables precise control over the morphology of metal silicide crystals by engineering surface defects on the substrate. The process begins with ion-beam patterning to create defects on Si(111) and Si(100) substrates, followed by the deposition of a thin metal oxide layer as the silicide precursor. Subsequent annealing in a hydrogen atmosphere reduces the oxide to metal, which then dewets and reacts with the silicon to form a silicide. Under these conditions, the silicide selectively nucleates and grows along the artificially introduced defects, which act as potential wells and determine the shape and positioning of the resulting structures. The effectiveness of AS-silicidation is demonstrated by the synthesis of NiSi₂ and its extension to Cu₃Si, illustrating the method's broad applicability to different silicides. This multistep process directly yields structured, low-dimensional silicides, eliminating the need for post-synthesis nanopatterning.

Nickel silicidation on large scales is conveniently achieved through a solid-state (SS) reaction of a thin film of nickel with a silicon substrate, triggered by annealing.^[3,4] At elevated temperatures, nickel atoms diffuse into the silicon bulk, resulting in a “supply-controlled” reaction, where the amount of metal initially deposited on the surface, referred to as the “metal sink” or reservoir, influences phase formation.^[5,6]

For many years, the study of nickel silicide focused primarily on being able to select the accurate phase^[7,8] and obtaining homogeneous silicide interfaces between silicon and metal interconnects in CMOS technologies.^[9–11]

However, advances in nanoscience have revealed that this class of materials holds potential in a wider range of technological applications, emphasizing the importance of adapting our methods to the new task of accurately controlling the material structuring.^[12]

In recent years, significant breakthroughs have deepened our understanding of silicide properties, while several others remain, for now, predicted only through theoretical studies. Among these materials, nickel silicide in its NiSi phase exhibits a rare high-temperature non-compensated antiferromagnetic ordering, highlighting its potential for future spintronics applications.^[13,14]

1. Introduction

Nickel silicides have been discovered in the 60's and have since attracted considerable attention in microelectronics for their low resistivities, ease of synthesis, and stability.^[1,2]

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Other silicides have also revealed promising behaviors: FeSi₂ nanosheets, for instance, exhibit ferromagnetism when thinned to a few atomic layers due to uncompensated spins.^[15,16] Similarly, tailoring the cobalt silicide/silicon interface in heterostructured nanoparticles has been shown to enhance both ferromagnetism and catalytic activity.^[17] Moreover, precise tuning of the manganese-to-silicon ratio during synthesis results in single crystals of the alternating Mn₃Si₅ phase.^[18]

It is now evident that the material's properties are determined by a complex interplay between the silicide phase and crystallinity,^[19] its morphology,^[20] and dimensionality,^[21–23] characteristics that on one side add a degree of tunability to these systems but that also complicate their controlled synthesis.

For most silicide applications, SS synthesis remains the most convenient and scalable approach, offering excellent material purity and compatibility with epitaxial growth. However, conventional SS-silicidation, typically performed by annealing a metal thin film on oxide-free silicon, produces continuous silicide layers that require additional patterning to form functional structures. This extra processing step increases complexity and can negatively affect material performance.

To address the challenges of post-synthesis patterning, direct laser writing has been successfully used to produce silicide nanostructures^[24] and 2D materials,^[25] with growth confined to the irradiated regions, highlighting the benefits of adding spatial control during material synthesis.

Interestingly, the silicidation reaction itself exhibits intrinsic selectivity mechanisms that can be strategically exploited to achieve spatial control during crystal growth, even without a localized heat source. Several studies have shown that factors such as the silicon surface free energy and the presence of native oxide layers strongly influence silicide nucleation.^[26] Current understanding suggests that the morphology of forming nanocrystals is governed by the dislocation arrays and lattice strain within the silicon substrate.^[27] The first stage of silicidation involves the interdiffusion of metal atoms into the silicon substrate. As the process progresses, a strain potential develops within the silicon lattice, driving further metal diffusion toward specific lattice sites where this potential is minimized.^[28] This strain potential not only dictates the morphology of newly formed nickel silicide crystals, which tend to nucleate along specific crystallographic planes^[29,30] but also influences their phase.^[31] For example, increased compressive stress to the silicon lattice is found to suppress the formation of silicide phases with large volume expansion in favor of NiSi₂, whose unit volume is similar to that of silicon.^[11]

The concept behind this study is to engineer such growth mechanisms to determine, prior to silicidation, the crystal growth according to the design specifications.

To achieve this, a new SS synthesis that allows the AS synthesis of NiSi₂ structures has been developed. With AS, we refer to a process capable of leading, without the need of any sacrificial layer, to the formation of a certain material, in our case NiSi₂, exclusively in desired areas. By shaping surface defects on silicon through ion-beam milling prior to silicidation, and by using atomic layer deposition (ALD) for the metal sink deposition, the NiSi₂ growth can be routed exclusively to the desired areas.

The technological value of this approach lies in achieving area-selectivity through a scalable SS synthesis. It allows for the direct integration of functional epitaxial silicide nanostructures into

conventional silicon wafers, without the need for post-synthesis processing. Moreover, the resulting silicide regions are embedded within a substrate that remains nearly morphologically unchanged, enabling added functionality without relying on complex multi-material stacking, opening new possibilities for device fabrication.

2. Results and Discussion

In this work, we show an experimental approach capable of promoting area-selectivity during the synthesis of nickel silicide.

This approach strategically leverages the native silicon oxide as a diffusion barrier toward nickel to control AS-silicidation. As shown in **Figure 1a**, the silicidation process is carried out on a pristine silicon wafer, without etching of the native oxide

Figure 1. SS synthesis of NiSi₂. a) Silicidation was carried out by depositing 4 nm of NiO on a pristine Si substrate, followed by annealing in a reducing atmosphere to promote NiO reduction, dewetting, surface diffusion, and finally NiSi₂ formation. b) Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrographs showing the different morphologies of NiSi₂ crystals depending on the silicon surface facet ((100) vs (111)). c) EDX map of the cross-section of a NiSi₂ crystal on Si(100). d) Ni dewetting and surface diffusion during reductive annealing. e) AS-silicidation can be attained by pre-patterning the Si surface using a FIB or other forms of local etching, followed by silicidation from NiO, leading to the formation of silicide crystals exclusively in the desired areas. f) NiSi₂ crystals obtained through AS-silicidation observed using CBS detector. g) FIB-fabricated surface defects that act as nucleation sites for NiSi₂ AS growth observed using ETD detector.

(1–2 nm) present on the surface. The presence of a SiO₂ barrier leads to a largely inhibited silicidation, which occurs predominantly on defective sites, leading to the formation of nanocrystals rather than a continuous silicide layer.^[4]

The entire SiO₂-inhibited silicidation process was carried out on a pristine silicon wafer (Figure 1a, step 1) upon coating the substrate with a 4 nm thick NiO film by ALD (Figure 1a, step 2). The choice of ALD is of crucial importance as this method provides excellent control over the NiO thickness, an important parameter for the later phase determination. The NiSi₂ formation is in fact a “supply-controlled” reaction, where the amount of Ni present on the surface affects the silicide phase equilibrium as well as the morphology of the areas converted into silicides.^[26] ALD is also key for ensuring the chemical binding of the deposited NiO thin film to the substrate, which is crucial to achieve selectivity, as we will show later. For simplicity, in this study, the thickness of the NiO sink (4 nm) was not varied, as it would otherwise have added another degree of freedom to the process. Finally, the silicidation reaction was carried out by annealing the sample at 620 °C while simultaneously injecting a reducing agent into the system (5% hydrogen in nitrogen gas) to reduce NiO to Ni and, in this way, promote reaction with the substrate (Figure 1a, step 3). This chemical transformation is key for unlocking area-selectivity of the growth in contrast to conventional SS-silicidation that is carried out by annealing metallic thin films on oxide-free silicon wafers, resulting in the immediate reaction between the two solids. In the presented case, the reaction dynamics are significantly different as silicidation occurs consecutively to nickel oxide reduction. Oxygen is removed from the NiO in the form of H₂O, and the newly formed Ni⁰ atoms remain weakly bound to the surface. The presence of native oxide on the surface is sufficient to hinder the formation of a NiSi₂ layer,^[3] resulting in the dewetting and clustering of Ni due to cohesive interactions being stronger than the adhesive interactions with SiO₂.^[32] Nickel atoms preferentially migrate toward defective regions where the native oxide is absent and underlying silicon is exposed.^[33]

These oxide discontinuities serve as dewetting templates where Ni atoms accumulate according to surface-energy minimization^[34,35] and consequently react, forming NiSi₂.

SEM analysis of pristine Si substrates subjected to the nickel silicidation process (Figure 1a, step 4) shows the formation of NiSi₂ nanocrystals that nucleate at SiO₂ defects generated during annealing. The resulting crystal morphologies are influenced by the surface orientation of the silicon substrates and the characteristic defects associated with each orientation. (Figure 1b, Figure S2, Figure S3).^[36]

If Si(100) is used, the NiSi₂ forms rectangular crystals that align along the two orthogonal [110] directions and extend into the bulk. The energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) map of the cross-section of a NiSi₂ crystal grown on Si(100) (Figure 1c) shows that the growth proceeds along the (111) plane, where the silicon lattice exhibits its largest interplanar spacing, thereby promoting nickel diffusion during silicidation. For this very reason, if Si(111) is used as a substrate, the bulk diffusion is limited, resulting in the formation of flat-lying NiSi₂ triangles and trapezoids (Figure 1b, Figure S4).^[37]

By introducing a patterning step before silicidation, the naturally occurring dewetting and diffusion processes can be directed

toward specific areas where defects in the SiO₂ layers have been intentionally introduced (Figure 1d). We refer to this methodology, comprising a patterning step followed by silicidation, as AS-silicidation (Figure 1e). Through Ar⁺ ion-beam milling, the native Si oxide can be locally removed from the surface, defining an energetically favorable nucleation site for NiSi₂ (Figure 1e, step 1). The rest of the sequence (Figure 1e, steps 2, 3, 4) proceeds analogously to the previous (Figure 1a), but in this case results in the formation of NiSi₂ crystals exclusively in the focused ion beam (FIB)-patterned defect sites (Figure 1f–g). A concentric backscattered electron (CBS) detector was used to image the strong compositional difference between the NiSi₂ nanostructures and the surface (Figure 1f). Using an Everhart-Thornley detector (ETD), the surface topography can be visualized, revealing circular defects (~9 nm deep) that act as templates for NiSi₂ crystal growth (Figure 1g). The ETD imaging also shows that the NiSi₂ crystals are almost entirely embedded within the substrate.

Compared with non-selective silicide formation (Figure 1b), AS-silicidation (Figure 1f) promotes the formation of large NiSi₂ crystals, whose growth depletes the surrounding area of the residual metal precursor.

To further elucidate the mechanism behind the AS-silicidation and explore new fabrication pathways, the sequence was applied to a Si(111) substrate with predeposited metallic structures in four different areas of the substrate (Figure 2a). Each structure was composed of four tantalum (Ta) contacts, each of them with a 200 × 200 μm square contact pad (used for contacting the electrical probe) and a contact arm on the opposite side (used for contacting the nano-micro structure). The spacing between the contact arms was 4 μm. These types of structures are typically fabricated to perform I/V characterization of conductive materials. Without any further processing, such structures have no functionality as long as no conductive material is placed between the contacts.

AS-silicidation was then applied, with the objective of pinning the NiSi₂ growth between the contact arms, creating a closed circuit. The growth area, a rectangular area (20 × 0.2 μm), which connects the 4 contact arms, was first irradiated using a FIB. A characterization of the optimal ion dose (proportional to the exposure time), required for completely removing the native oxide from the surface was performed (Figure 2b). Atomic force microscopy (AFM) was employed to characterize the surface after milling. Four different doses were applied: 40, 10, 1 and 0.1 pC μm⁻². As can be observed from the AFM micrographs, a dose of 40 pC μm⁻² corresponds to a defect depth of 3.5 nm (Figure S5), while a reduced dose of 10 pC μm⁻² creates a well of 1 nm (Figure S6). When the ion exposure is further reduced to 1 pC μm⁻², the modified area bulges from the surface as a consequence of surface amorphization due to Ga⁺ ion implantation^[38] and carbon deposition,^[39] resulting from the beam exposure (Figure S7). For the smallest dose of 0.1 pC μm⁻², the modified area is characterized by a broad bulging and by the presence of a few isolated voids (Figure S8). For the two smallest doses (1 and 0.1 pC μm⁻²), AFM analyses suggest that native silicon oxide is still partially present, and the surface primarily underwent amorphization.

Consistent with the approach described in Figure 1e, AS-silicidation was carried out by coating the sample with 4 nm of NiO, followed by reductive annealing at 620 °C (Figure 2c).

Figure 2. Device fabrication pathway starting from the modification of a pre-existing structure. a) 40 nm thick Ta contacts were deposited on Si(111). The magnified areas show the dimensions of the contacts. b) FIB was used to mill a trench between the contact arms to pin the silicidation to the desired area. On the right-hand side of the figure, AFM scans of the surface after milling correlate defect depths to the FIB area doses used for the patterning. c) After modification, the sample was coated with 4 nm of NiO and annealed for 20 min at 620 °C in a gas mixture of 5% H₂ and 95% N₂. d) The resulting structures for the four different area doses.

The ALD conditions (step 2) and annealing procedure (step 3) were consistent with those used in the previous experiments. At the end of AS-silicidation, NiSi₂ structures formed in the FIB-exposed areas between the contacts (Figure 2d). Evidently, the morphological difference between these crystals is related to the FIB-modified areas, as this was the only parameter that was varied. Doses of 40 and 10 pC μm⁻² gave rise to the formation of a continuous nickel silicide structure, while smaller doses (1 and 0.1 pC μm⁻²) resulted in dispersed NiSi₂ structures. This result is consistent with the AFM measurement which shows noticeable differences between higher (40 and 10 pC μm⁻²) and lower (1 and 0.1 pC μm⁻²) ion doses, where the defective area is not a continuous trench.

To obtain a single NiSi₂ structure, the milling depth should at least match the native oxide thickness (1–2 nm),^[40] thereby fully exposing the underlying Si.

The NiSi₂ structure formed with a 10 pC μm⁻² dose was selected for two-probe resistance measurements (Figure 3a), as it exhibited a continuous silicide formation with minimal damage to the contact arms. The measurements confirmed electrical continuity across each of the four contacts (labeled 1–4).

EDX analysis of the device revealed that the Ni L signal was confined to the silicide structure grown along the FIB trench (Figure S9), as well as in isolated NiSi₂ nanosheets formed at remote defect sites (Figure S10). No Ni signal was detected outside the silicide regions, indicating that any residual surface Ni was below the detection limit of the instrument. Since the electrical measurements were performed in air, any such Ni traces would have oxidized into highly resistive NiO ($\rho = 10^4$ – 10^6 Ω cm) and therefore would not have contributed to the conduction.

For comparison, electrical measurements were also performed on a control sample, patterned using identical FIB and ALD conditions but without AS-silicidation (Figure 3b). In this case, no current was detected, effectively ruling out parasitic conduction from FIB-induced contamination or leakage through the Si substrate.

These results confirm that the current observed in Figure 3a originates from the NiSi₂ structure bridging the contacts.

It can be observed that the resistance ($R \equiv V/I$), extrapolated from the I/V curves (Figure 3a, bottom), is in the range of 10–30 kΩ. The measured R is not ideally proportional to the channel length (l). Considering two neighboring contacts (1-2), the measured R_{12} is 21 kΩ, which is higher than the $R_{13} = 10$ kΩ, measured

Figure 3. Two-point resistance measurements of a) NiSi_2 nanostructure grown between contacts after using the optimal ion dose of $10 \text{ pC } \mu\text{m}^{-2}$ for defect fabrication, showing electrical contact, and b) open-circuit conditions before silicidation.

between two contacts with double distance (1–3). This deviation is attributed to increased contact resistance, a problem that could be mitigated without altering the fabrication process by designing contacts with optimal work-function alignment and adhesion to silicide.

To further investigate the state of the TallNiSi_2 interfaces, as well as the silicide crystal structure, a transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis of the cross-sectioned area below contacts 1 and 2 (Figure 4a, inset), cut along the (110) plane, was carried out.

The NiSi_2 structure was found to extend several hundred nanometers into the bulk of Si, and to be closely interfaced with the four Ta contacts (Figure 4a). This result by itself is remarkable, as it demonstrates that the experimental procedure can serve as a top-down strategy for creating embedded silicide regions functionally contacted with other interfaces. This approach opens the possibility of forming contacts between adjacent materials through tailored chemical reactions, rather than relying on precise physical alignment. Interface formation could be governed with atom-scale precision by the inherent chemical properties of the materials, thereby reducing the risk of misalignment and fabrication defects typically associated with conventional patterning and deposition methods.^[41] Such chemically guided interface formation enhances both the robustness and scalability of device integration.

In this study, the TallNiSi_2 interface exhibits particles and voids (Figure 4c), which have been identified as the primary cause of increased contact resistance, an issue that could be mitigated by etching the SiO_2 layer prior to contact deposition.

The NiSi_2 structure is visibly composed of different grains, showing that during silicidation, the material grows along

different lattice orientations. This phenomenon is not expected to occur on Si(111), where NiSi_2 is known to form crystalline nanosheets, lying flat on the (111) surface facet (Figure 1c). This is likely related to the expansion of the silicon lattice resulting from NiSi_2 nucleation in the FIB-irradiated areas. The energetically favorable nucleation sites introduce a significant amount of metal into the lattice, leading to the buildup of strain potential, which, according to previous studies, is likely the primary driver of Ni bulk diffusion into Si during silicidation.^[42] Another contributor to the development of a polycrystalline structure that can be identified is that the FIB-induced trench is not aligned with any of the [110] crystallographic directions along which the material tends to grow as a single crystal (Figure S11).^[43,44] The region shown in Figure 4b features a NiSi_2 nanosheet oriented parallel to the Si(111) plane and aligned along the [110] directions. This crystal likely represents the initial nucleation center, whose growth, misaligned with the trench direction, induces lattice strain that promotes further nucleation along different lattice planes.

High resolution TEM imaging of the $\text{NiSi}_2\|\text{Si}$ interface in [110] zone, together with electron diffraction (Figure 4d), were used to identify the phase of the silicide as well as the epitaxial nature of the interface $\text{NiSi}_2(110)\|\text{Si}(110)$ (Figure 4e).

The formation of the NiSi_2 phase at 620°C deviates from its phase formation temperature of $700\text{--}800^\circ\text{C}$ reported in certain studies.^[5,45] This result, once again, points to the lattice strain generated during AS-silicidation, which promotes the formation of the epitaxial phase characterized by minimal volume expansion, which corresponds to the NiSi_2 phase.^[11] For the investigated $\text{NiO}\|\text{Si}$

Figure 4. TEM analysis of a) Cross-sectioned area of the NiSi₂ structure between two contacts. b) NiSi₂ nanosheet epitaxially interfaced to the silicon lattice. c) Ta/NiSi₂ interface. d) Phase identification of NiSi₂ through high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF). e) Atomic structure of the NiSi₂/Si interface.

system, the NiO reductive annealing temperature can be lower than 620 °C, giving a wide temperature range for studying phase formation during AS-silicidation (Figure S12).

Defects aligned along favorable crystallographic directions or exhibiting radial symmetry do not impose geometric constraints on crystal growth, thereby reducing strain potential buildup and, in turn, suppressing bulk diffusion. This facilitates the AS growth of NiSi₂ nanosheets, which, due to their unconstrained epitaxy (Figure S4), are oriented parallel to the (111) plane (Figure 5a).

The possibility of determining the morphology and dimensionality of low-dimensional silicide systems prior to their synthesis, using surface defects as templates, would be a pivotal change in device fabrication based on silicides. In fact, recent theoretical

studies on 2D silicides have also emphasized the importance of refining synthesis methods, as the material properties are highly dependent on achieving a fine balance between the number of atomic layers and the crystal morphology.^[15,16] For such application, silicide layer growth and top-down etching are not adequate,^[41] while instead AS-silicidation would allow to obtaining of a “ready-made” epitaxial silicide of pre-determined shape, grown directly at the desired surface location.

To expand the library of metal oxides that can lead to AS-silicidation, ALD of CuOx was also tested as a metal sink on Si(100). With SEM/EDX (Figure 5b), we confirmed AS-silicidation and formation of copper silicide (identified as Cu₃Si)^[46] that nucleates along a defect area. As highlighted in the inset, unconstrained

Figure 5. a) NiSi_2 nanosheets AS grown on Si(111). b) Cu_3Si structure on a FIB-modified area of Si(100) obtained using AS-silicidation.

Cu_3Si crystals on Si(100), similarly to NiSi_2 , have a square shape with the four sides aligned along [110].

The evidence that this Cu_3Si can also be grown selectively on defects offers a solid base to hypothesize that this methodology could be applied to further silicides.^[47] Knowing that the phenomenon that leads to area-selectivity is the dewetting of a metal from an oxide surface, whose free energy minimization is related to silicide formation, it is thus expected that analogous phenomena would apply to other transition metals. Iron-group silicides are expected to be well suited for AS-silicidation, as they have been reported to exhibit epitaxial self-alignment during silicidation,^[48–50] low-temperature dewetting on silicon oxide,^[51–53] and high diffusivity in silicon.

3. Conclusion

In summary, a new methodology of AS-silicidation that enables control of morphology and growth region of NiSi_2 crystals on Si(100) and Si(111) has been developed. Surface defects are identified as the nucleation sites for NiSi_2 crystals. More specifically, this study emphasizes the role of native silicon oxide in the discrimination between nucleation sites (absence of native silicon oxide) and non-nucleation sites (presence of native silicon oxide). The use of ALD for the deposition of nickel oxide is key for unlocking this unique AS growth. We attribute the surface re-arrangement of nickel in the FIB-modified areas to the increase of free energy deriving from the chemical transformation of NiO (chemically bound to the surface through ALD) to loosely bound metallic Ni, which is stabilized only by defective areas where it is in direct contact with the Si lattice. The role of ALD in forming a first silicide phase during the deposition step cannot be excluded, as this technique is sensitive to the chemistry of the surface and the deposition is carried out at a temperature that is sufficiently high to promote silicidation. The formation of an initial nickel-rich phase (Ni_3Si or Ni_2Si) during ALD may be another contributor to the pinning of the silicide growth in the FIB patterned areas. The use of ALD for depositing the metal oxide sink ensures atomic-level control over the thickness and amount of the material, which is phase-determining during SS-silicidation reactions and becomes even more critical when targeting the production of 2D structures.

Lattice strain effects, deriving from the interstitial diffusion of Ni into Si, are likely the main driving force for promoting NiSi_2 phase formation as well as its increased polycrystallinity. Different processing parameters, such as the thickness of the NiO thin film and the annealing conditions, need to be characterized to study the formation of nickel-rich phases (Ni_2Si and NiSi).

This methodology has been proven to be implementable in multistep fabrication, offering a novel approach to modifying pre-existing structures in a top-down manner. The potential of this approach includes the production of nanostructured silicides of controlled morphology and precise substrate positioning. By applying this procedure at the outset of a more complex fabrication scheme, a silicon substrate can be locally functionalized with embedded silicide domains. This results in minimal topographical differences, allowing for subsequent layers to be built without issues, while imparting distinct properties to the functionalized areas.

This approach, being derived from a well-established SS synthesis protocol, has the benefit of being reproducible and cost-effective, offering strong potential for scalability even to industrial scale.

Future work will focus on obtaining different nickel silicide phases. After the successful AS synthesis of Cu_3Si , we will study the adoptability of this approach to other metal silicides of technological relevance that are expected to be compatible with AS-silicidation.

4. Experimental Section

The substrates, *p*-doped (boron) 4-inch Si wafers (resistivity: 1–30 Ω cm), were purchased from Photon Export. The thickness of the native oxide on the surface of the silicon wafers is specified as 1–2 nm. The wafers were cut into 10 × 10 mm pieces (in the following “substrates”), which were cleaned by acetone/isopropanol (IPA)/water rinsing in cleanroom conditions (ISO7).

Surface patterning was performed using two different approaches.

One approach consisted of direct patterning of the surface with a focused Ga^+ ion beam (FIB) in a dual beam SEM/FIB FEI Helios 450S (Thermofisher, USA), operated at 30 kV of accelerating voltage and 0.43 nA of current.

The second approach was lithographic patterning. The silicon substrates were coated with a double layer of PMMA 950 A2/PMMA 495 A4 via spin-coating. Resin was cured by heating to 180 °C for

5 min on a hot plate. The samples were patterned using electron beam lithography with a 150TWO tool (Raith). The electron gun setup was 10 kV of accelerating voltage and 30 μm aperture. To selectively remove the resist from the electron-irradiated areas, the development was carried out by dipping the samples into a 1:3 solution of methylisobutylketone (MIBK)/IPA for 45 s, followed by a 45 s dip into pure IPA. To remove material from the silicon surface, the samples were etched for 500 s with an Ar^+ ion beam in an ion-beam etching tool (4wave inc.) The ion gun was set to an accelerating voltage of 300 V and 50 mA of beam current (15 sccm Ar flow). The stage was set at an angle of 10° and 15 rpm rotation speed. After ion milling, the resist was removed with acetone.

For the electrical characterization of NiSi_2 , 40 nm Ta contacts were deposited through sputtering (AJA ACT 2200 UHV) on top of a patterned resist (following an analogous procedure as described above).

For the Ni sink deposition, 4 nm thick NiO films were deposited by ALD in a custom-made setup at 210°C at a growth per cycle (GPC) value of 1.49 Å. The precursors for the ALD process were bis-cyclopentadienyl nickel(II) (CAS# 1271-28-9, Strem), sublimed from a hot source at 60°C , and O_3 produced from O_2 using an ozone generator (OzoneLab, Ozone Services, Yanco Industries).

For the Cu sink deposition, CuOx was also deposited using ALD at a reactor temperature of 140°C . The precursors were bis(dimethylamino-2-propoxy) copper(II) (CAS# 185827-91-2, Strem), sublimed at 60°C , and O_3 .

The SS synthesis of NiSi_2 was performed by 20 min long thermal annealing of the silicon substrates, coated with NiO, at a temperature of 620°C under continuous flow of 0.5 lpm of a reducing gas composed in volume by 5% H_2 % and 95% N_2 (Nippon Gases). Cu_3Si was synthesized by 20 min long thermal annealing at 900°C under continuous flow of 1 lpm of the reducing gas mixture. The annealing setup was an infrared-heated furnace (Mila-5000, Ulvac-Riko).

SEM/EDX analysis was carried out using the FEI Helios 450S microscope with an accelerating voltage of 5 kV and a current of 50–100 pA. The EDX signal was collected by an EDAX Octane Pro detector. FIB Cross-sections and lamella were fabricated using the FIB at an accelerating voltage range of 30 to 5 kV and at electron currents ranging from 2.5 nA to 18 pA. TEM characterization was performed in an FEI Titan microscope (ThermoFisher, USA) operating at 300 kV.

The transport measurements were performed in a LakeShore probe station at 25°C . This system features tips controlled by micrometric actuators that allow us to contact the devices and conduct two-point resistance measurements. The tips are connected to the measuring instrumentation via triaxial cables. To minimize sample degradation and reduce noise in the measurements, the system was evacuated to below 2×10^{-5} mbar. The electrical measurements were conducted using a Keithley 4200-SCS (semiconductor characterization system) equipped with three source-measurement units (SMUs). LabVIEW programs developed at CIC nanoGUNE were used to control the measurements and acquire the data.

To measure the depth of the FIB trenches, AFM was employed in AC mode. The measurements were carried out using a NanoWizard V (JPK-Bruker) with cantilevers of spring constant 2.8 N m^{-1} , resonance frequency of 75 kHz, and tip radii of 2 nm (all nominal values) (SuperSharp Enhanced-soft, Nanotools, NanoAndMore). The experiment was conducted on $1.5 \times 1.5 \mu\text{m}$ areas. The obtained data were analyzed using the JPK data processing software. The depth values of the four trenches were calculated as 3, 0.8, 0.1, and 0 nm, respectively.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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ALD, altermagnets, area-selective growth, nickel silicide, silicides

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